

ARSF Data Archive

● NEODC archives and distributes ARSF data from 1982 to present:

- Digital Aerial Photography
- Scanned Analogue Aerial Photography **NEW**
- CASI
- ATM
- LiDAR

ARSF ATM, Wytham Woods, Oxfordshire

ARSF aerial photograph. New Biggin, Northumberland

Data Services

- Register, search the NEODC catalogue and request access to ARSF data on www.neodc.rl.ac.uk
- Web service for on-line use of AZ software **NEW**
Allows simple use of AZGCORR and AZEXHDF to geocorrect and orthorectify ATM & CASI L1b data to L3a
- NEODC datasets are available for free download to registered users. Access restrictions apply to some data.
- We welcome email enquiries : neodc@rl.ac.uk

NEODC airborne data coverage map

Layer: ARSF Analogue Aerial Photography						
#	Date	Project code	Frame #	Location (lon lat)	Preview	Data
1	1995-05-03	95_24	6832	-1.988524 55.767238 [Show Google Map]		Full image
2	1999-09-17	95_24	6058	-1.994262 55.747599 [Show Google Map]		Full image
3	1995-07-17	95_24	7906	-1.992889 55.764936 [Show Google Map]		Full image

Layer: CASI L1b products					
#	Filename	Date	Product details	Bounding box (xmin xmax ymin ymax)	
			Processing level: L1b		
			Aircraft: G-NERC		
			Pilot: H. Christensen		
			Base: Coventry		

